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2 **Intensification of sulfate radical based-advanced oxidation treatments**
3 **at pilot scale for simultaneous disinfection, removal of contaminants of**
4 **emerging concern and antibiotic resistance genes**

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22 **Abstract**

23 Wastewater reuse is becoming an important solution to the water scarcity problem. However,
24 contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) in treated water, such as pathogens and antibiotic
25 resistance genes (ARGs), are a potential health and environmental risk. To ensure the safety of
26 this practice, the EU has passed Regulation (EU) 2020/741, which sets standards for the reuse of
27 wastewater for agricultural purposes. Moreover, to address this issue, sulfate radical-based
28 advanced oxidation processes (SR-AOPs) are being explored as a promising solution. This study
29 evaluates the effectiveness of different pilot-scale SR-AOP, based on the combination of
30 peroxymonosulfate (PMS) with O_3 and H_2O_2 , for the simultaneous elimination of
31 microorganisms, CECs, and ARGs in actual urban wastewater treatment plant (UWWTP)
32 effluents. In addition, the phytotoxicity was assessed to determine whether the treated water is
33 suitable for reuse in agriculture. The PMS/ O_3 system demonstrated the ability to remove total
34 aerobic microorganisms in 20 min and *Escherichia coli* in 5 min, 94% of CECs as an average,
35 and 6 out of the 8 ARGs, reducing the risk associated with wastewater reclamation. However, the
36 system showed phytotoxicity, inhibiting seed growth by 10-30%, probably associated with the
37 by-products formed in the reaction between organic matter and ozone. The combination of PMS
38 and H_2O_2 in the presence of UV-A improved the system's disinfection effectiveness, compared to
39 PMS/UV-A, especially using a molar ratio 1:3 (0.5 mM-PMS:1.5mM- H_2O_2), achieving complete
40 elimination of total aerobic microorganisms in 90 min. However, this double oxidation system,
41 does not improve CECs and ARGs removal compared to PMS/UV-A in neither of the two molar
42 ratios studied (1:1 or 1:3). Additionally, none of these treatments (PMS/UV-A or PMS/ H_2O_2 /UV-
43 A) significantly reduced the prevalence of ARGs.

44 **Keywords:** water reclamation; ARGs; CECs; disinfection; sulfate radical; ozone.

45

46 **1. Introduction**

47 In the context of increasing occurrences of droughts in several European Union (EU) member
48 states, wastewater is emerging as a viable alternative water source [1]. The reuse of water obtained
49 from urban wastewater treatment plants (UWWTPs) can help alleviate the problem of water
50 scarcity by ensuring a safe and predictable water supply, while also relieving the burden on water
51 bodies and improving the resilience of the EU to climate change. Moreover, the practice of
52 treating wastewater and reusing it in a suitable manner can extend the lifespan of water resources
53 and reduce their depletion rates [2–4]. By doing so, it has the potential to provide a sustainable
54 and cost-effective solution to the ever-growing demand for water resources in the EU.

55 The EU has recently passed a regulatory act, namely the European Regulation (EU) 2020/741 [5],
56 which aims to establish standardized legal requirements regarding the reuse of wastewater for
57 agricultural irrigation purposes only. Alongside this, the new regulation seeks to harmonize
58 minimum monitoring requirements, risk management provisions, permitting requirements, and
59 transparency provisions. These measures intend to assess and address potential additional health
60 and environmental risks that may arise from such practices, while also making key information
61 on every water reuse project publicly available. It is noteworthy that the regulation has been in
62 effect since June 2020, although its applicability began on June 26, 2023. In Spain, this new
63 regulation is set to replace the existing RD 1620/2007 [6], which outlines the physicochemical
64 and microbiological parameters for the reuse of wastewater in agricultural, urban, industrial,
65 recreational, and environmental domains.

66 Despite the stricter physicochemical and microbiological quality standards established for the
67 reuse of reclaimed water, the presence of many other contaminants, frequently detected in treated
68 water and not yet regulated, may represent a risk to the environment and human health [1]. In this
69 regard, several studies have reported a considerable content of pathogens [7–10] and contaminants
70 of emerging concern (CECs) [11–15], including antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) [16–18], at
71 the outlet of UWWTPs. These contaminants, which until now went unnoticed, are increasingly
72 being analysed. In fact, although no concentration limit values are established, the Regulation

73 (EU) 2020/741 refers, for the first time, to the potential risk associated with the presence of CECs,
74 microplastics, and pesticides, among others.

75 Recently, the sulfate radical-based advanced oxidation processes (SR-AOPs) have been the focus
76 of attention due to their promising potential for the degradation of emerging contaminants,
77 organics and biological, across a wide pH range, due to the higher redox potential (2.5–3.1 V) of
78 sulfate radical ($\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$) when compared to hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$) [19]. The predominant reaction
79 mechanism of $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ with organic compounds is electron transfer, which contributes to its high
80 selectivity. In contrast, $\cdot\text{OH}$ is a non-selective radical that can react with organic compounds
81 through hydrogen abstraction or electrophilic addition [20].

82 Peroxymonosulfate (PMS; HSO_5^-) is the main precursor for the generation of sulfate radicals [19].
83 Despite its potential as oxidizing agent, PMS exhibits low reaction rates when reacting directly
84 with organic contaminants, requiring the use of appropriate activation methods including, among
85 others UV, thermal or microwave activation [21–25], metal-based catalysts [26–29],
86 carbonaceous-based materials activation [30], and double oxidation systems [20,31].

87 Recently, the intensification of SR-AOPs through the above-mentioned double oxidation systems,
88 by incorporating other oxidants such as H_2O_2 and O_3 has been proposed. The aim is to increase
89 the rate of contaminant removal with a lower concentration of reagents, reducing the impacts
90 (environmental and economic) of the process. Some authors have reported the successful
91 activation of PMS using O_3 for the removal of organic and biological pollutants [20,32–39] or the
92 synergistic effect of combining PMS and H_2O_2 for the same purposes [31,40,41]. However, to the
93 best of our knowledge, there are no reports comparing treatments combining PMS with O_3 and
94 H_2O_2 for the simultaneous disinfection and removal of CECs and ARGs from real wastewater. It
95 is noteworthy that most of the manuscripts reported in the literature are based on the application
96 of treatments at the laboratory scale, using model contaminants (biological or organic) and
97 simulated water matrices separately [42].

98 The main objective of this study is to evaluate the efficacy in the simultaneous elimination of
99 pathogenic microorganisms and CECs (including ARGs) through the application of pilot scale
100 SR-AOPs in real wastewater effluents. Under these conditions, different treatments combining
101 the use of PMS in combination with radiation and with other oxidants (namely H₂O₂ and O₃) have
102 been evaluated. The effectiveness of the treatments on actual treated wastewater samples is
103 studied, determining the simultaneous kinetics removal of naturally occurring microorganisms,
104 CECs and ARGs. Finally, phytotoxicity studies will demonstrate whether the treated water has
105 the potential for reuse in agriculture.

106 **2. Material and methods**

107 **2.1. Proposed treatments and chemicals**

108 In this research, 4 different SR-AOPs, namely PMS/UV-A, PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A (in two different
109 molar ratios, 1:1 and 1:3) and PMS/O₃, were used. These systems were previously optimised in
110 the same pilot plant for the inactivation of *Enterococcus faecalis* in simulated wastewater [43].
111 Potassium peroxymonosulfate (PMS) was used as the main oxidant, using two concentrations,
112 0.5 and 1.5 mM. This compound is marketed by Sigma-Aldrich as a triple potassium salt (KHSO₅-
113 0.5KHSO₄-0.5K₂SO₄; Oxone[®]). Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30% v/v, Chem-Lab) was used in
114 combination with PMS at a concentration of 1.5 mM. The O₃ dose applied was 0.25 g·h⁻¹.

115 **2.2. Wastewater samples**

116 Actual water samples were collected between October 2021 and March 2022 from a UWWTP
117 located in central Spain. This UWWTP counts with a sequence of primary and secondary
118 treatments based on the use of activated sludge. The samples were freshly collected early in the
119 morning to ensure as little variations as possible on their characteristics throughout the
120 experiments. Table 1 shows the average values of the physicochemical and biological
121 characterisation of the UWWTP secondary effluents during the 20 days of sampling. The
122 physicochemical characterisation was carried out by the analytical laboratory of the UWWTP,
123 while the microbiological characterisation was carried out in the laboratories of the Universidad
124 Politécnica de Madrid following the process described in section 2.3.1.

125 **Table 1.** Physico-chemical and biological characterisation of secondary treated wastewater
 126 samples.

Parameter	Units	Value
pH		6.92 ± 0.13
Conductivity	μS·cm ⁻¹	801 ± 127.11
Total suspended solids (TSS)	mg·L ⁻¹	2 ± 1
Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)	mg·L ⁻¹	4 ± 0.71
Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)	mg·L ⁻¹	12.38 ± 0.85
P _{total}	mg·L ⁻¹	10.29 ± 4.62
N-NH ₄	mg·L ⁻¹	0.5 ± 0.39
N-NO ₃	mg·L ⁻¹	5.1 ± 0.93
N _{total}	mg·L ⁻¹	8.68 ± 0.64
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	CFU·mL ⁻¹	2.25·10 ³ ± 1.79·10 ³
<i>Enterococcus sp.</i>	CFU·mL ⁻¹	6.57·10 ¹ ± 4.62·10 ¹
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	CFU·mL ⁻¹	1.57·10 ¹ ± 9.03·10 ¹
Total aerobic bacteria	CFU·mL ⁻¹	1.25·10 ⁵ ± 4.41·10 ⁴

127 2.3. Analytical procedures

128 Throughout this work, the efficacy of the proposed treatments in the removal of pathogenic
 129 microorganisms and CECs (including ARGs), has been evaluated.

130 2.3.1. Microbiological analysis

131 Three different bacteria, two Gram-positive (*Enterococcus sp.* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and
 132 one Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) were analysed and controlled, as well as the Total Aerobic
 133 Bacteria parameter. The concentration of the bacteria along the treatments was determined using
 134 the drop plate method [44] through a 10-fold serial dilution in sterile saline solution (NaCl 0.9%),
 135 and when needed, followed by the spread plate method (*Standard Method 9215C*) to increase the
 136 detection limit (DL), *i.e.*, 100 CFU·mL⁻¹ and 10 CFU·mL⁻¹, respectively. *E. faecalis*
 137 quantification was made over the selective culture media Slanetz & Bartley agar (Condalab;
 138 Spain), *E. coli* over MacConkey agar (Scharlau; Spain), and *Staphylococcus aureus* over
 139 hypersaline Mannitol Agar (Scharlau, Spain). Finally, the determination of Total Aerobic Bacteria

140 was made using Plate Count Agar (Scharlau, Spain). The colonies formed were counted after
141 incubation at 37°C during 24 h for *E. coli* and 48 h for the rest of microbiological parameters.
142 Analyses were performed in triplicate and the standard deviation of the results was calculated,
143 plotted in graphs as error bars.

144 **2.3.2. ARGs analysis**

145 Several genes, commonly detected in wastewater effluents, and responsible for encoding
146 resistance to quinolone (*qnrS*), sulphonamides (*sulI*), β -lactams (*bla_{TEM}*), cephalosporins (*bla_{CTX-M32}*),
147 carbapenems (*bla_{OXA-48}* and *bla_{VIM}*) and tetracycline (*tetM*) antibiotic classes, and class 1
148 integron integrase (*intI1*) [45], as well as the 16S rRNA gene, were analysed following procedures
149 described elsewhere [46]. Briefly, the first step was to filter 100 mL of each water sample on 0.27
150 μ m polycarbonate membranes (MPC020047H, CHMLAB GROUP S.L., Barcelona, Spain). DNA
151 extraction was performed using the commercial DNeasy® PowerWater® Kit (QIAGEN Sciences
152 Inc., MD, USA), following the procedure described by the manufacturer. The total DNA extracted
153 was measured using a NanoDrop® Lite specialised spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, MA,
154 USA). Analysis of the concentration of ARGs was performed by real-time quantitative
155 polymerase chain reaction (PCR) on a 7500 Fast Real-Time PCR machine (Applied Biosystems,
156 Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.), using 7500 Software v2.0.6. The genes analysed in this study, as
157 well as the conditions used during the PCR analyses, are listed in Table S1 (Supplementary
158 material). Amplification data were analysed by calculating the ratio of each analysed ARG to the
159 16S rRNA gene (indicator of total microbial abundance), using the cycle threshold (*Ct*) value.
160 The *Ct* represents the activation cycle number at which the fluorescent signal is detectable.

161 **2.3.3. CECs analysis**

162 The detection and quantification of CECs (150 compounds) were performed by UHPLC (Exion
163 LC AC, Sciex, Foster city, CA, USA) coupled to mass spectrometry (MS) detection, using a
164 quadrupole-linear ion trap analyser (UHPLC-QqLIT-MS/MS) also from Sciex (5500 QTRAP™)
165 as previously applied in Verdú et al., [47]. Briefly, a Luna Omega Polar column (100 \times 2.1 mm,
166 1.6- μ m particle size, Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) was used and the mobile phase consisted

167 of 0.1% of formic acid in Milli-Q water (eluent A) and methanol (eluent B) at a flow rate of
168 0.3 mL·min⁻¹. The applied gradient was as follows: 5% (B) (kept 1 min); from 5% (B) to 100%
169 (B) in 7 min (kept 4 min); from 100% (B) to 5% (B) 0.5 min (kept 5 min). The total analysis time
170 was 17.5 min. The injection volume was 10 µL. The column oven temperature was 30 °C and the
171 autosampler was operating at 15 °C.

172 The electrospray source (Turbo IonSpray) was operated in positive mode (ESI+) as follows: ion
173 spray voltage (IS), 5500 V; source temperature, 550 °C; CAD gas, medium; ion source gas 1
174 (GS1), 50 psi; ion source gas 2 (GS2), 50 psi and curtain gas, 20 (arbitrary units). Nitrogen was
175 used as a nebulizer gas, curtain gas and collision gas. The multiple reaction monitoring (MRM)
176 mode and the Scheduled MRM™ Algorithm were used for the acquisition of the samples. An
177 MRM detection window of 40 s was applied, and the target scan time was of 1 s. To confirm the
178 analytes, the criteria indicated by the European Union guidelines for pesticide residue analysis
179 (SANTE/12682/2019) were used: two SRM transitions with the expected retention time and an
180 appropriate ion ratio (tolerance ± 30%). Prior to analysis, all samples were filtered (0.22-µm PTFE
181 syringe filters, Aisimo, London, UK). Analyte quantification was accomplished by matrix-
182 matched standard calibration (standards prepared from 10 to 1000 ng·L⁻¹). Blank subtraction and
183 sample dilution were applied when necessary. As injection standard, ¹³C-caffeine was added to
184 all samples. For data acquisition and processing, Analyst 1.7.1. and Sciex OS (both from Sciex)
185 were used, respectively.

186 This research does not evaluate in detail the elimination of each individual pollutant, but rather
187 quantifies the reduction of the total load. However, a complete list of the compounds analysed
188 and their concentrations before and after each of the treatments is given in Table S2
189 (Supplementary Material).

190 **2.3.4. Phytotoxicity analysis**

191 Phytotoxicity assessment was carried out using the seed germination method, based on the
192 germination of seeds of *Solanum lycopersicum* (tomato) and *Raphanus sativus* (radish) species,

193 following the methodology described by Ghanbari et al. [48]. Briefly, for each specie and sample,
194 15 seeds were placed in a Petri dish on which a filter paper had been previously placed, and 10
195 mL of the sample to be analysed were added. The seeds were incubated for 72 h at 25°C ($\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$).
196 After this time, the shoots were carefully separated with the help of forceps and photographed.
197 The open-source software ImageJ, an image processing program, was used to measure their
198 length. The length increase is determined using Equation 1:

$$199 \quad \Delta L (\%) = \frac{\frac{\sum L_s}{G_s} - \frac{\sum L_c}{G_c}}{\frac{\sum L_c}{G_c}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

200 The variables G_s and G_c represent the count of germinated seeds in the treated effluent and control
201 conditions, respectively. Meanwhile, L_s and L_c denote the length of the radicle in the treated
202 effluent and control conditions, respectively.

203 **2.4. Pilot plant**

204 A pilot plant developed by APRIA Systems (Photobench LED275-0.8/LED365-16/450-16a) was
205 employed in this research. The plant is equipped with a single feed pump (CM 1-3; Grudfos;
206 nominal flow rate of 1,700 L·h⁻¹ and a maximum operating pressure of 16 bar) that establishes a
207 constant flow within the system by pumping water through different treatment modules. The
208 pump is safeguarded by a safety filter (NW25, Cintropur) positioned downstream to optimize
209 treatment efficiency and protect vulnerable parts of the system by preventing the passage of solids
210 larger than 25 μm .

211 The main components of the plant are two parallel ring photoreactors, each with two concentric
212 tubes, where the inner tube houses the LED lamps while the water to be treated flows through the
213 outer tube. One reactor features an LED lamp emitting ultraviolet radiation in the UV-C region
214 while the other has an LED lamp capable of emitting both ultraviolet radiation in the UV-A region
215 and radiation in the visible spectrum. In this research, only the UV-A and UV-Vis photoreactor
216 was used, which consists of 20 UV-A LEDs ($\lambda = 365\text{-}370 \text{ nm}$, $\text{Irad} = 1,200 \text{ mW}$) and 20 Vis
217 LEDs, arranged alternately in 4 rows. The theoretical maximum radiation emitted by the UV-A,
218 and Vis lamps is 1,973 W·m⁻² and 2,969 W·m⁻² respectively. However, the total irradiated power

219 can be adjusted for each experiment. The reactors are enclosed in a black polylactic acid casing.
220 An air-cooling system positioned at the top, equipped with a temperature probe, ensures the
221 maintenance of LED irradiation potential, and prolongs their lifespan. The recommended
222 maximum operating flow rate for each reactor is 650 L·h⁻¹, with a maximum pressure of 1 bar.

223 Additionally, the plant incorporates an ozone generation unit, which can be utilized independently
224 or in conjunction with the photochemical treatment. The ozone generator (GHBZO3-E,
225 ZonoSistem) can produce an adjustable ozone dose, with a maximum flow rate of 2.5 g·h⁻¹. A
226 Venturi tube is employed for in-line dosing of the generated ozone. To regulate the gases
227 produced during the process, an in-line air extractor, equipped with a Kosner activated carbon
228 filter (model KE-100), is also included.

229 Moreover, the installation allows operation under temperature-controlled conditions, facilitated
230 by a heat exchanger, thermostatic bath, and an external temperature probe. The plant incorporates
231 a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) to monitor, control, and regulate the temperature and
232 power consumption of the LED lamps. Furthermore, an online controller, comprising a pH and
233 temperature probe, as well as an analytical transmitter, is present to display the values collected
234 by the probe (both from Mettler-Toledo).

235 **3. Results and discussion**

236 **3.1. Microorganisms removal**

237 The average microorganisms concentration recorded for all samples analysed is shown in Table
238 1. As they are real samples collected days apart, the observed deviation is relatively high, although
239 the population of the different species always remained within the same order of magnitude. To
240 be able to compare the results of the different treatments, standardized initial values have been
241 established, depending on the observed concentration. Thus, for *E. coli* this value was set at 10³
242 while the population of total aerobic microorganisms was around 10⁵ CFU·mL⁻¹. The presence of
243 *Enterococcus sp.* and *S. aureus*, on the other hand, is significantly lower, always below 100
244 CFU·mL⁻¹. Although their elimination was monitored during the treatments, all treatments

245 evaluated (except the exclusive application of UV-A radiation) achieved elimination up to the
246 detection limit ($< 10 \text{ CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) in less than 5 min. Therefore, the focus has been paid on the
247 inactivation of the species present at higher concentration.

248 Figure 1 shows the inactivation of *E. coli* (Figure 1a) and total aerobic microorganisms (Figure
249 1b) for all treatments except those involving the use of ozone. All treatments were able to reduce
250 the *E. coli* population below the detection limit in 30 min or less. In contrast, only one of the
251 evaluated systems achieved total aerobic microorganism removal. It was the PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A
252 (molar ratio 1:3) system that achieved the best results, surpassing the efficiency of the system
253 with a higher PMS concentration (molar ratio 1:1). The efficiency of the PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A system
254 stems not only from the synergistic effect of adding two oxidants that can be activated under
255 irradiation conditions, as shown in equations 2-4, but also as a result of the reaction that occurs
256 between PMS and hydrogen peroxide itself, as described in reaction 5. This reaction theoretically
257 promotes the generation of a sulfate radical and three hydroxyl radicals.

262 However, the result obtained over total aerobic microorganisms contrasts with the results
263 observed when applying the same treatments on simulated wastewater samples [43]. In that study,
264 the efficiency of PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A (molar ratio 1:3) was consistently lower in terms of
265 microorganism removal compared to the PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A (molar ratio 1:1). In the previous
266 study on treatment optimization in simulated water [43], it was demonstrated that when using a
267 molar ratio of 1:3 (PMS:H₂O), the SO₄^{•-} was the predominant species in the disinfection process.
268 On the other hand, when using a 1:1 molar ratio, the [•]OH gained greater importance in the
269 disinfection process. Therefore, in the present study, a similar formation of radical species in the

270 process should be observed. However, the difference in disinfection behavior compared to the
 271 study with simulated water lies precisely in the aqueous matrix. The real wastewater used in the
 272 present study, being a more complex matrix with higher concentrations of organic and inorganic
 273 matter than the simulated one, may exhibit a scavenger effect that more significantly affects the
 274 hydroxyl radicals. As a result, a lower performance with the 1:1 ratio treatment may be obtained.

275
 276 **Figure 1.** Inactivation of naturally occurring a) *E. coli* and b) Total aerobic microorganisms in
 277 wastewater samples. Experimental conditions: [PMS] = 0.5 and 1.5 mM; [H₂O₂] = 1.5 mM; pH
 278 ≈ 7 ; Radiation intensity = 1,900 W·m⁻². DL: Detection Limit.

279 From the results obtained here, it can be concluded that the sulfate radicals have been found to be
 280 less sensitive than the hydroxyl radicals to matrix change. This fact is in line with the theory
 281 presented by other authors³ that sulfate radicals are more selective for the degradation of certain
 282 pollutants [49]. On the other hand, the PMS/UV-A system, whose mechanism of action is mainly

283 based on non-radical pathways, lost almost all its disinfectant power when using a real matrix,
284 achieving a reduction in the microbiological population of just over 1- logarithmic reduction value
285 (LRV).

286 Figure 2 shows the inactivation of *E.coli* (dotted line) and total aerobic microorganisms (solid
287 line) by O₃ alone and the PMS/O₃ system. It can be clearly observed how the addition of PMS in
288 combination with O₃ manages to increase the reaction kinetics compared to the treatment with
289 ozone alone. Thus, it is important to highlight the result obtained regarding the total aerobic
290 microorganisms, where it is observed that with ozone alone a reduction of 2.7-LRV is achieved
291 in 30 minutes, but by adding PMS, the detection limit (5-LRV) is reached in 20 minutes of
292 reaction. The same trend can be seen for the elimination of *E. coli* (dotted line). Although in this
293 case, both treatments can eliminate this bacterium, it can be seen that by combining the two
294 oxidants this is achieved in only 5 min, while twice as much time is needed if only ozone is used.
295 These results agree with the obtained un the previous investigation conducted under the same
296 conditions but with simulated wastewater [43], both O₃ alone and the PMS/O₃ system were able
297 to eliminate the *E. faecalis* population in less than 30 min. As described in the mechanistic study
298 conducted on simulated water [43], both ozone and the hydroxyl radical are reactive species that
299 promote the bacterial inactivation process. Under the operating conditions studied in this research,
300 with pH close to 7, the presence of the hydroxyl radical is expected to be relevant, originating
301 from the radical pathway of ozonation. Furthermore, when PMS is added to the system, the sulfate
302 radical is expected to appear in the process through the reaction of its dissociated form with ozone,
303 as shown in equations 6-10.

309

310 **Figure 2.** Inactivation of microorganisms in real wastewater using the PMS/O₃ system. Dotted
 311 line: *E. coli*; Solid line: total aerobic microorganisms. Experimental conditions: [PMS] = 0.5
 312 mM; O₃: 0.25 g·h⁻¹; pH ≈ 7.

313 3.1.1. Antibiotic Resistance Genes removal

314 The selected ARGs were detected in all the actual freshly samples collected from the secondary
 315 treatment of the UWWTP in this study. The following order of abundance was observed: *intl1* >
 316 *sulI* > *bla_{TEM}* > *qnrS* > *tetM* ≈ *bla_{OXA-48}* ≈ *bla_{CTX-M32}* ≈ *bla_{VIM}* (Table S3, supplementary material).
 317 A particular behavior was observed for *qnrS*, which was no detected in the samples collected and
 318 used for the O₃ and PMS/O₃ treatments. Since the presence of the gene is generally very low, the
 319 main reason for not appearing in such samples may be due to analytical error or simply because
 320 it is below the limit of quantification. It could also be a consequence of seasonality, but the study
 321 is not large enough to be able to corroborate this.

322 Figure 3 shows, for treatments not involving ozone, the relative abundance of genes detected at
 323 higher concentrations in the samples. The individual efficiencies of radiation (1) and PMS (2)
 324 have been included in the graphs for comparison. The relative abundance of the three non-plotted
 325 ARGs can be extracted from Table S3 (Supplementary Material).

326

327 **Figure 3.** Relative abundance of ARGs before and after treatments: 1) UV-A; 2) PMS (1.5
 328 mM); 3) PMS (1.5 mM)/UV-A; 4) PMS (1.5 mM)/H₂O₂/UV-A; 5) PMS (0.5 mM)/H₂O₂/UV-A.

329 Experimental conditions: [H₂O₂] = 1.5 mM; pH ≈ 7; Radiation intensity = 1,900 W·m⁻². DL:

330

Detection Limit.

331 As seen in the previous section for the removal of microorganisms, the treatment that returns the
 332 best result is the combination of 0.5 mM PMS with H₂O₂ and UV-A irradiation. However, none
 333 of the treatments can achieve a competitive removal compared to the results reported in the
 334 literature. In the research carried out by Berruti et al. [46], complete elimination of most of the
 335 tested genes was achieved using UV-C/PMS, requiring less than 60 min. The difference with the
 336 results reported here is very large, probably due to the use of radiation with a higher energy input
 337 in the PMS absorption range. With a treatment like Berruti et al., [46], Rodríguez-Chueca et al.

338 [50] did not obtain such favourable results. However, the disparity in the results shown by both
339 authors is probably due to the low contact times used by Rodríguez-Chueca et al. (4 - 18 sec)
340 compared to the time required for the treatment proposed by Berruti et al. (60 min of treatment
341 equivalent to 300 sec of contact with the radiation, having used a recirculating reactor).

342 Hu et al. [51] also combined PMS with UV-C radiation, achieving the elimination of up to 3.1
343 log of the *sull* gene and 3.3 log of the *intI1* gene. This is evidence that UV-C radiation allows
344 much better results in the elimination of ARGs. The treatments evaluated here (PMS/UV-A or
345 PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A) achieve the inactivation of microorganisms, but they are not sufficiently
346 effective in this field. Although, due to the scarcity of articles dealing with the use of
347 PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A, it has not been possible to find information in the literature on the efficacy of
348 this system in the removal of ARGs, it could be expected that, by modifying the treatment to
349 combine it with UV-C, more promising results would also be obtained.

350 The situation is very different when using ozonation and when the use of O₃ and PMS is
351 combined, as in both cases most genes have been eliminated (below the limit of detection) within
352 30 min of treatment (Figure 4). The only genes that could be quantified after this time were *16S*
353 *rRNA* and *intI1*, reducing the concentration of the former by almost 34% for both treatments.
354 Although the relative abundance of the reference gene decreased similarly, the PMS/O₃
355 combination resulted in a more pronounced deletion of the *intI1* gene, which translated into a 78%
356 increase in *Ct* compared to the 66% observed in the case of ozonation. It is important to emphasize
357 the significance of reducing the prevalence of the *intI1* gene, as it acts as a gene that promotes the
358 horizontal transfer of other resistance genes. Therefore, reducing this gene facilitates the
359 prevention of gene transfer with other bacteria.

360 On this occasion, in addition to the initial samples, water samples were taken after the addition of
361 PMS (but before starting the ozonation). A few minutes after the addition of the oxidant, a sample
362 was taken out to verify that the PMS (by itself) does not modify the genetic load in the water.

363 After analysing and comparing the samples, no relevant differences were observed before and
364 after the addition of the reagent for any of the genes evaluated (results not shown).

365 The removal of ARGs by ozonation has been widely studied, obtaining good results that have
366 been published in numerous articles [52–54]. However, although the combination of this
367 technology with other elements (US, UV, H₂O₂, etc.) is becoming increasingly common [55],
368 only one publication reporting the evaluation of the PMS/O₃ system for the removal of ARBs and
369 ARGs has been found at the time of writing this paper. The study published by Oh et al. [56]
370 compares the efficacy of O₃, PMS/O₃, O₃/PS and O₃/H₂O₂ in the removal of the pB10 plasmid as
371 an indicator of resistance. Among the treatments evaluated, PMS/O₃ was the best performer,
372 eliminating 2 log in 15 min.

373 Given the increase observed in recent years in the study of the potential of this system for
374 wastewater treatment, it is expected that the number of investigations evaluating its capacity to
375 eliminate an increasing number of ARGs will also increase.

376

377 **Figure 4.** Relative abundance of ARGs before and after treatment of a real secondary effluent
378 using the PMS/O₃ system. Experimental conditions: [PMS] = 0.5 mM; O₃: 0.25 g·h⁻¹; pH ≈ 7.

379 3.1.2. Removal of contaminants of emerging concern

380 Figure 5 shows the reduction in the total load of contaminants detected in the real effluent after
381 the application of the evaluated treatments. It can be seen that the UV-A radiation alone achieves
382 a degradation of 45% of the contaminants. On the other hand, PMS is only capable of removing
383 15% of the total load. In both cases, an increase in the concentration of some of the compounds
384 evaluated was observed, when they are transformation products (TPs) generated during the
385 treatment. This is the case, for example, of tramadol N-oxide, a TP generated in the degradation
386 of the opioid drug tramadol. These results highlight the importance of evaluating TPs during
387 treatments. On the contrary, some contaminants were completely removed by direct oxidation
388 with PMS. Therefore, a 100% degradation of ciprofloxacin and erythromycin was obtained when
389 applying UV-A and PMS.

390

391 **Figure 5.** Overall contaminants removal by the different treatments evaluated at pilot scale: 1)
392 UV-A; 2) PMS (1.5 mM); 3) PMS (1.5 mM)/UV-A; 4) PMS (1.5 mM)/H₂O₂/UV-A; 5) PMS
393 (0.5 mM)/H₂O₂/UV-A; 6) O₃; 7) PMS/O₃ (0.5 mM). Experimental conditions: [H₂O₂] = 1.5
394 mM; O₃: 0.25 g·h⁻¹; pH ≈ 7.

395 The combination of PMS and UV-A increased the contaminant degradation rate to 71%. Although
396 the generation of radicals, largely SO₄⁻ and [•]OH, is limited in this treatment according to the
397 results previously reported by Guerra-Rodríguez et al. [43], synergies between the two elements

398 can occurs, as it was observed for the inactivation of microorganisms in simulated wastewater.
399 However, it is striking that the addition of H₂O₂ to the treatment causes a decrease in the
400 degradation capacity of the process. Using the PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A system, total contaminant
401 removal decreased to 59% and 22% when using PMS concentrations of 1.5 and 0.5 mM,
402 respectively. This fact differs from the results of disinfection and elimination of ARGs, since in
403 both cases the best results were obtained when using this system with a PMS concentration of 0.5
404 mM.

405 Unlike PMS, and although it is far from its peak absorbance, H₂O₂ shows some absorbance at the
406 working wavelength (Figure S2; supplementary material). Thus, competition for radiation could
407 translate into fewer photons available for contaminant degradation.

408 A similar phenomenon was identified by Rodriguez-Chueca et al. [50] when evaluating the
409 photochemical activation of PMS for wastewater treatment, since better results were obtained by
410 applying UV-C radiation individually than in combination with the oxidant. However, this effect
411 was observed in the ARGs elimination, but not in the degradation of contaminants. In this case,
412 the absorption of radiation at 365 nm by H₂O₂ is extremely low, so the phenomenon of
413 competition for photons does not seem likely to occur.

414 The low degradation obtained by the PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A system (1:3) suggests that the sulfate
415 radicals generated have a certain selectivity towards the microorganisms while are not so effective
416 in the degradation of the organic microcontaminants. It must be however considered that the water
417 used in the different treatments was collected on different days. Although no major differences
418 were observed in the composition between samples, a higher number of replicates would be
419 necessary to discard an effect of the matrix in the treatment efficiency.

420 In the case of ozone, almost all pollutants (89%) were degraded, while the addition of 0.5 mM
421 PMS to the treatment resulted in an increase in efficiency to 94% degradation, this represents an
422 increase in performance of 5.6%. These results agree with those achieved by Yang et al. [57] on
423 the removal of biocides by PMS/O₃. In this study, an increase of 11.6% in the degradation

424 efficiency of chloro-methyl-isothiazolinone (CMIT) was observed when combining the two
425 oxidants ($[O_3]_0 = 42 \mu\text{M}$, $[PMS] = 0$ or $21 \mu\text{M}$) over a secondary effluent. Deniere et al. [35] also
426 observed an improvement in the performance of the PMS/ O_3 system compared to ozonation for
427 the removal of organic pollutants, specifically 12% on secondary effluents, using $64 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of
428 PMS and a concentration higher than $10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of O_3 . Therefore, the results reported in the
429 present research are in line with those of other authors, confirming the efficiency benefit of the
430 combination of both reagents.

431 Contrary to what occurred in the other treatments evaluated, when ozone was used, the formation
432 of TPs such as tramadol N-oxide was not observed, which seems to indicate greater mineralization
433 of the contaminants under the experimental conditions tested. Even so, and although most of the
434 contaminants were removed, some compounds turned out to be particularly recalcitrant. Such is
435 the case of lamotrigine, nicotinamide and sulphamethoxazole, which were found in the treated
436 effluent.

437 In view of the results obtained, it is possible to affirm that, once again, the treatment combining
438 PMS/ O_3 is the one that allows a greater elimination of microcontaminants. Similarly, it should be
439 noted that the PMS/ H_2O_2 /UV-A system, capable of inactivating aerobic microorganisms and, to
440 a lesser extent, eliminating ARGs, has not shown favourable results in the removal of emerging
441 contaminants in real concentrations.

442 3.2. Phytotoxicity analysis

443 The phytotoxicity analysis using seeds of two different species (*R. sativus* and *S. lycopersicum*)
444 was carried out to assess the quality of the treated effluent and its potential as a source of water
445 for crop irrigation.

446 All *R. sativus* seeds germinated, both when irrigated with treated and untreated water (Table S4,
447 supplementary material). Nevertheless, a higher sensitivity of *S. lycopersicum* seeds was
448 observed. Neither UV-A radiation nor the addition of PMS at a concentration of 1.5 mM, the
449 treatments used as a blank, influenced germination. On the other hand, for all other treatments

450 involving the use of PMS, an increase in the number of germinated seeds was observed when
451 irrigated with treated effluent compared to those irrigated with raw secondary effluent.
452 Specifically, when analysing the results obtained for the PMS/H₂O₂/UV-A systems, an increase
453 of more than 100% can be observed, indicating a decrease in phytotoxicity.

454 On the contrary, there is a clear increase in the toxicity of the effluent after treatment with ozone,
455 which is reflected in a decrease in the number of germinated seeds. This increase in toxicity was
456 not only reflected in the number of canisters obtained, but also in a decrease in their length (Figure
457 6). For the calculation of the variation, only the length of the germinated shoots was considered.
458 Thus, for the PMS/O₃ treatment, for example, the average of the 11 sprouts germinated in the
459 untreated effluent was calculated and compared with the average length of the 6 sprouts obtained
460 in the treated effluent. When evaluating the ozone-treated effluent, a growth inhibition of almost
461 60% for *S. lycopersicum* sprouts and about 30% for *R. sativus* was observed. This inhibition is
462 less pronounced after treatment with PMS/O₃, reducing plant length by 10-30%.

463 One potential drawback of ozonation is the formation of organic and inorganic by-products, which
464 may pose a health risk. Several studies have shown that the phytotoxicity of the effluent tends to
465 increase after ozone treatment, due to the oxidation of organic matter, specially bromates and
466 nitrosamines [52,58], but also due to by-products generated during the degradation of pollutants.
467 Our main hypothesis is that in this case phytotoxicity is associated with the generation of
468 substances such as bromate or nitrosamines. As mentioned above, the generation of by-products
469 from the degradation of organic pollutants is ruled out as lower concentrations of tramadol N-
470 oxide (Table S2, supplementary material) were observed in the processes studied with ozone than
471 in the other treatments. This hypothesis is supported by the results obtained by Mao et al. [36] in
472 a study of iopamidol degradation by PMS/O₃ treatments. They found that the PMS/O₃
473 combination reduces the formation of toxic by-products from iopamidol compared to the use of
474 ozone alone, due to the action of SO₄⁻ and [•]OH on their degradation. Again, these observations
475 are consistent with the results corresponding to the formation of tramadol N-oxide (Table S2,

476 supplementary material). The O₃/H₂O₂ system has also been shown to reduce toxicity compared
477 to ozone treatment alone, due to increased mineralization of the pollutants [59].

478

479 **Figure 6.** Variation in growth of water-irrigated shoots before and after treatments: 1) UV-A; 2)
480 PMS (1.5 mM); 3) PMS (1.5 mM)/UV-A; 4) PMS (1.5 mM)/H₂O₂/UV-A; 5) PMS (0.5
481 mM)/H₂O₂/UV-A; 6) O₃; 7) PMS/O₃. Experimental conditions: [H₂O₂] = 1.5 mM; O₃: 0.25 g·h⁻¹;
482 pH ≈ 7.

483 Focusing attention on treatments that do not involve ozonation, it is appropriate to recall that
484 previously our research group, after treating a secondary effluent using the PMS/UV-A LED
485 system, achieved an increase in shoot growth of around 18-30% [25]. This phenomenon did not
486 occur in this case; on the contrary, a slight decrease in shoot length was observed for both species
487 studied. Although there are several factors that may explain this, it should be noted that this
488 decrease is in any case less than 10%, which may be within the acceptable margin of error in the
489 measurement techniques used and does not constitute a significant decrease in length. Firstly, the
490 difference may be due to the increased dose of PMS used during treatment (1.5 mM vs. 0.1 mM).
491 On the other hand, when characterizing the water samples used in both studies, it was found that
492 the organic matter load in the water used by Guerra-Rodríguez et al. [25] is approximately three
493 times higher than the one used here (Table 1). This higher organic matter load may favor shoots
494 growth [60]. It should also be noted that the species used for the phytotoxicity analyses are

495 different in both studies, so a comparison of the results obtained is not reliable, as different species
496 may react differently to the same treatment.

497 Among the treatments evaluated, PMS/O₃ can eliminate contaminants, microorganisms, and
498 genes more efficiently and quickly. However, although the toxicity is significantly lower than that
499 derived from ozone treatment alone, to implement this treatment, it would be necessary to have a
500 post-treatment capable of reducing the phytotoxicity (such as an activated carbon filter) to make
501 the effluent useful for irrigation. This would increase the cost and environmental impact of the
502 treatment, thus reducing the advantages over other AOPs. Some authors are already evaluating
503 the addition of more elements during treatment, such as carbonaceous materials [61], or the use
504 of pre-treatments [62], to inhibit the formation of brominated compounds during the process.

505 **4. Conclusions**

506 This study highlights the application of SR-AOPs as an alternative to conventional tertiary
507 treatments for wastewater reclamation, demonstrating the capacity to simultaneously remove
508 pathogenic microorganisms, CECs and ARGs, minimising the risks of wastewater reclamation
509 and further reuse in agriculture.

510 The PMS/O₃ system was able to inactivate the total aerobic microorganisms present in a real
511 secondary effluent in 20 min, and *E. coli* in 5 min. At the same time, it achieved the elimination
512 below the detection limit of 6 out of the 8 ARGs evaluated (*sulI*, *bla_{TEM}*, *tetM*, *bla_{OXA-48}*, *bla_{CTX-}*
513 *M32*, *bla_{VIM}*), reducing the concentration of 16S rRNA by 34%. Additionally, the reduction of *intI1*
514 helps to reduce the horizontal transfer of other resistance genes. Furthermore, also the PMS/O₃
515 system resulted in the removal of the highest number of CECs, with an average removal of 94%.

516 In relation to the treatments combining PMS and H₂O₂ in the presence of UV-A, the results
517 obtained by the PMS/UV-A treatment improve at the level of disinfection. The PMS/H₂O₂/UV-
518 A treatment (molar ratio 1:3), together with PMS/O₃, was the only one that achieved the complete
519 elimination of total aerobic microorganisms, but in a time of 90 min. However, at the level of

520 CECs removal, the PMS/UV-A process achieved a better performance (74%) than when
521 combined with H₂O₂ (59%, 1:1 ratio; 22% 1:3 ratio). In any case, none of the treatments was able
522 to reduce the prevalence of ARGs.

523 However, phytotoxicity tests revealed a weakness of the PMS/O₃ system, as it was observed that
524 its application has a negative effect on water quality, inhibiting seed growth by 10-30%. This may
525 be due to the generation of by-products because of the reaction of ozone with organic matter. This
526 inhibition increases to 60% when the water is treated with O₃ alone, so the combination of both
527 reagents is beneficial to the system due to the action of both sulfate radicals and ozone, although
528 subsequent treatments should be considered to reduce this phytotoxicity.

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539

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